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Employment is the activity of people that does not contradict the Constitution and the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, related to the satisfaction of their personal and social needs, bringing them earnings (labor income). According to the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan have the exclusive right to dispose of their abilities for productive and creative work and to carry out any activity not prohibited by law, including those not related to the performance of paid work.¹

Agriculture is a branch of the economy aimed at providing the population with food and obtaining raw materials for a number of industries. It is important to note that agriculture is one of the most important industries in almost all countries of the world. In the modern world, the agri-food sector, which includes agriculture, food and light industry, plays a vital role in the economy of Uzbekistan. In 2019, its share in the country's

EMPLOYMENT IN AGRICULTURE

Barakayeva Dilbar Hafizovna¹

Subhonova Hushnuda Subkhonzoda²

¹ Senior teacher SamISE

² Student of SamISE

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ABSTRACT

This article highlights the importance of employment in agriculture, how it affects the development of the economy of Uzbekistan and the way of development of agriculture.

GDP was the largest at 41%, and it accumulated 19% of all export earnings. Agriculture alone now accounts for 28% of GDP. It employs more people than any other industry - 27% of the total workforce, or more than 3.65 million citizens. Despite the dire socio-economic consequences of the coronavirus pandemic for Uzbekistan, this industry continues to be an important driver of economic growth. It is projected to grow by 2.8% in 2020, compared with 0.6% growth in national GDP.

One of the advantages in agriculture is the ability to create more jobs than is currently happening. It is estimated that through thoughtful government support and investment in the agri-food sector, 700,000 to 1.3 million new workers can be employed annually. This is more than enough to solve the issue of creating jobs for 600 thousand young people who annually replenish the labor market throughout the country. The value of agriculture lies not only in the number of jobs created here. Employment in this sector has a stronger impact on reducing

¹ <https://www.lex.uz/acts>

poverty and inequality than in any other industry. About 80% of the country's low-income citizens live in rural areas, and their income is almost entirely dependent on agriculture. Due to the coronavirus outbreak in 2020, poverty rates in Uzbekistan are projected to rise for the first time after declining over twenty years. The experience of various countries confirms that economic growth in agriculture helps to reduce poverty by 2-3 times. This figure is higher than in any other sector of the economy. Thus, agricultural jobs not only help to reduce poverty, but also expand the opportunities for wider participation of the rural population in various economic processes. This rule is no exception in the case of Uzbekistan. So, what does the country need to do to achieve these goals?²

The total state control and insufficient level of public investment in agriculture, which existed until recently, have significantly reduced potential employment in the country's agri-food sector. Under the government procurement system, farmers were required to engage in monoculture production, growing cotton and wheat, and selling crops at low government prices. These crops are among the least profitable and at the same time the least labor intensive. In turn, the productivity of other crops was lower, since the land for them was allocated without taking into account the local conditions for their cultivation.

Population of the Republic of Uzbekistan as of January 1, 2021 is 34 million 558 thousand people, of which 49.4% are in rural areas and 50.6% live in the city. Employment of people living in rural areas, the increase in their well-

being is carried out directly due to the ongoing economic and social reforms. Labor distribution by sector has changed in recent years. However, in our country agriculture is the main part of the workforce. The labor force in the Republic of Uzbekistan is 52.8% of the total population. With their conscious, purposeful activities, they make a significant contribution to the development of agriculture, as well as other sectors, increasing its efficiency. With the adoption of the

Employment Program by the Government of our country, great attention is paid to the use of labor resources in rural areas. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-308 of March 23, 2006 "On measures to stimulate an increase in the livestock population in personal assistants, collective farms and farms."³

According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 4947 on the development strategy, where the 3 priority includes the modernization and intensive development of agriculture. According to which the country will pay special attention to:

- strengthening the food security of the country;
- expansion of the production of an environmentally friendly product;
- increasing the export potential of the agricultural sector
- further optimization of sown areas, aimed at reducing the sown area for cotton and grain crops, with the placement of potatoes, vegetables, fodder and oilseeds, as well as

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<https://blogs.worldbank.org/ru/europeandcentralasia/how-create-more-jobs-and-reduce-poverty-uzbekistan-focus-agri-food-sector>

³ Agricultural economics (N.Nurmatov)

new intensive orchards and vineyards on the released lands;

- creation and introduction of new varieties of agricultural products resistant to diseases and pests, etc.

It is important to point that, factors of increasing labor productivity in agriculture include:

- natural and climatic conditions;
- rational placement of agricultural crops on land, efficient use of arable land and irrigated land;
- acceleration of production;
- improving the quality of the material and technical base;
- implementation of scientific and technological development achievements;
- professional Development;
- improving the organization of work and material incentives.

The issue of increasing labor intensity in agriculture is very vital and is based on the specifics of this sector:

-Agriculture is currently the most diversified sector of the economy. This means that the problem of labor intensification is solved in different ways everywhere: in some cases it is self-employment as an incentive (agriculture, on its own territory; in these places the owner often works for free), in others - an increase in wages.

-Russia lags far behind developed countries in the production of agricultural machinery. For example, 10 tractors are installed per 1000 hectares of arable land, and in the USA - 36. Due to the low level of technical equipment in agriculture, more than 250

technological operations are performed manually in crop production. At the same time, labor costs are 4 times higher than in American farms.

The growth of agricultural production in the United States is mainly due to the growth of the material and technical base, the use of the achievements of scientific and technological progress, and the intensification of agricultural labor. Based on this, over the past 20 years, labor costs in certain sectors of agricultural production have decreased by 2-3 times.⁴

We think that in order to ensure employment for the population in rural areas, special attention should be paid to the introduction of innovative technologies in the agricultural sector. At the same time, improve the skills of local workers so that they can competently use the limited resources of the land to grow better quality products for the satisfaction of society. In addition, it is necessary to create conditions for farmers to have accurate and timely data on the opportunities and requirements for products in export markets, climatic

⁴ Economic Agriculture R. X. Yergashev

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